

DIRECT TRANSLATION PROCEDURES

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Annotation.

This article is interpreted on the basis of the issues of general linguistic description of translation procedures. It expresses features as the translation, strategies, sentences, range of perspectives and have been assigned a multitude of labels, among which we have procedures, techniques, strategies, processes and methods. the type of text, the purpose of the translation and the nature of the readers and words in translation of meaning on the logical basis of lexemes.

Keywords.

Literal translation, linguistic services, oblique translation, transposition, modulation, equivalence, adaptation, proficiency, cognitive categories.

Introduction

Literal translation. This occurs when ST is translated 'word-for-word' into TT. Literal translation is commonly used in languages of the same family and culture. Literal or word-for-word translation is the directly transferring of source language text into a idiomatically and grammatically proper target language text in which the translator's task is limited to observing the adherence to linguistic services of the foreign language. In principle, a literal translation is a unique solution which is reversible and complete in itself. A literal translation is commonly applied when translating between two languages of the same family and even more so when the languages also share the same culture.

When the literal translation is not applicable, Vinay and Darbelnet introduce the second category of translation strategies which include oblique translation, which includes four further procedures of translation: transposition, modulation, equivalence, adaptation.

Transposition is the first technique towards oblique translation. It operates at grammatical level and it involves the replacement of a word class of one part of the speech for another without changing the original message. Translators change the word type, for instance verbs for nouns or nouns for prepositions. The transposed

phrase loses its original value, however, the meaning is the same. In short, transposition is a translation procedure, where a part or some parts of the original speech change their sequence in the translation process. This method requires the proficiency in both the source and the target language and mastery of the translator to know whether the replacement of the word category is conceivable in the TT without changing the meaning of the original message. It involves replacing one word class with another without changing the meaning of the message. There are two types of transposition, namely obligatory and optional transposition. Obligatory transposition occurs when the target language has no other choices because of the language system.

Materials And Methods

Modulation. Whereas transposition is a shift between grammatical categories, modulation is a shift in cognitive categories. Vinay and Darbelnet postulate eleven types of modulation: abstract for concrete, cause for effect, means for result, a part for the whole, geographical change, etc., This translation technique consists in the variation of the form of the original message by modifying the point of view without changing the meaning. It basically means a change of perspective: the translator uses a phrase that is different in the source and the target languages in order to transfer the same idea. This strategy involves a shift in both the semantics and the point of view of the source language. Modulation is a variation of the form of the message, obtained by a shift in the point of view. This change can be justified when the close translation results in a grammatically correct text, but it is considered unsuitable, unidiomatic or awkward in the target language.

Equivalence. This accounts for the same situation using a completely different phrase. This term is used by Vinay and Darbelnet to refer to cases where languages describe the same situation by different stylistic or structural means. An utterance of the ST is replaced in the TT with one that fulfils the same pragmatic function, although it differs in form and meaning. This strategy is commonly used for the translation of idioms, proverbs and the onomatopoeia of animal sounds. "Equivalence is not a set of criteria which translations have to live up to, but is rather a group of features which characterizes the relationships linking the TT with its ST. It is applied by using an entirely different structure with different meaning from that of source language text so long as it is considered appropriate in the communicative situation equivalent to that of the source language.

Adaptation. A shift in cultural environment, i.e., to express the message using a different situation, e.g. cycling for the French, cricket for the English and baseball

for the Americans. This term to refer to the translation strategy that implies changing the cultural reference when the cultural-specific peculiarities of the source text do not exist in the target culture and they must be eliminated or replaced by other cultural-specific peculiarities appropriate in the TT. Vinay and Darbelnet exemplify this technique with the cultural connotation of sport games in different countries: English - Cricket, French - Cyclisme, American-Baseball.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Adaptations are particularly common in the translation of film and book titles. The adaptations intend that the translated titles make sense and are attractive to read for the target audience. Regarding the degree of change in the TT, theorists distinguish two methods of adaptation: “global adaptation, where the ST suffers a total change of its function in the TT, and local adaptation that only affects certain parts and sections of the ST. These basic procedures are complemented by other procedures. Except for the procedures of compensation and inversion, they are all classified as opposing pairs. It is adopted when the object or situation referred to in the source language is unknown in the target language culture. In such a case the translator has to create a new expression for a new situation that can be considered equivalent.

Compensation. An item of information, or a stylistic effect from the ST that cannot be reproduced in the same place in the TT is introduced elsewhere in the TT. An element from the ST is placed elsewhere in the TT. This element may be “an item of information or a stylistic effect from the ST that cannot be reproduced in the same place in the TT. The technique of compensation is used to avoid a translation loss. Losses in translation are sometimes inevitable, since there might be terms, which do not have natural or obvious equivalents in the TT.

4. CONCLUSION

Concentration vs. Dissolution. Concentration happens when an expression from the ST is translated with a shorter number of words in the TT. This entails the production of a more economic text in the TT. A common example of concentration is the use of compound words and hyphens to translate prepositional verbs, adjectival, adverbial or prepositional phrases. Dissolution occurs when an expression from the ST is translated with more words in the TT in order to rephrase an idea or strengthen the sense of a word or expression from the ST, when its correspondence in the TL cannot be transferred as accurately.

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